

DMP4NFDI

NFDI Basic Service for Data Management Plans

DMP/SMP tool hosting, template standardisation, support and training for NFDI consortia

Proposal for the Integration phase of a Basic Service in Base4NFDI

Submitted: January 22nd 2025

1 General Information

- **Name of proposed Basic Service (in English):** NFDI Basic Service for Data Management Plans
- **Acronym of the proposed Basic Service:** DMP4NFDI
- **Service "subtitle" explaining key functionality:** DMP/SMP tool hosting, template standardisation, support and training for NFDI consortia
- **Corresponding NFDI Section:** Section Common Infrastructures
- **Lead institution:** TU Darmstadt, Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek, Magdalenenstr. 8, 64289 Darmstadt
- **Name of lead institution principal investigator:** Prof. Dr. Thomas Stäcker, direktion@ulb.tu-darmstadt.de
- **Participating institutions**

Principal Investigator	Institution, location	Contact E-mail	Member in [consortium] ¹	Funding requested [yes no]
Prof. Dr. Thomas Stäcker	TU Darmstadt, Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek, Darmstadt	direktion@ulb.tu-darmstadt.de	NFDI4ING	yes
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Table 1: List of participating institutions

- **Initialisation Phase:** June 2024 - May 2025
- **Planned duration of the integration phase:** July 2025 - June 2027

¹ Name one DFG consortium the institution is or has a route to become a member of and through which funds should be appropriated if this proposal is approved.

Statement on efforts required by consortia for integration of service

In order to make use of DMP4NFDI to establish a DMP or SMP service for their communities, the consortia need to provide resources regarding three aspects. 1) For setting up a consortium RDMO client, rather small personnel resources are needed to customise the frontend theme, providing information, and a contact person regarding login or community-AAI and general page contents. Integrating RDMO with the consortium service portfolio needs additional technical personnel resources depending on complexity. For this, we offer and highly support incubator projects. 2) Although many templates already exist, we recommend the adaptation or development of community-specific templates. DMP4NFDI will support this development, but outreach to the community and adding discipline-specific contents can only be carried out with the necessary scientific background. The time and personnel needed for development depends highly on community experience and needs. 3) The consortia should set up appropriate support structures for DMPs or SMPs, e.g. via helpdesk and training. DMP4NFDI will act as secondary and third level support. In addition, DMP4NFDI offers train-the-trainer workshops, regular four-weekly jour fixes to support service development and exchange between the consortia.

Summary of the proposal in English and German

The Basic Service DMP4NFDI supports the NFDI consortia by providing services aligned to Data Management Plans (DMPs), Software Management Plans (SMPs), and related concepts. In particular, DMP4NFDI hosts a multi-tenant instance of the open source tool RDMO that can be tailored to domain-specific needs. In addition to RDMO, DMP4NFDI services include a consulting supporting the creation of templates as well as content standardisation, complemented with training and materials for DMP/SMP responsible staff in the NFDI consortia. The DMP4NFDI service portfolio aims to facilitate the creation of discipline-specific DMP/SMP templates using standardised, machine-actionable, and interoperable formats, as well as to support and improve communication between the different stakeholders and services involved in research data management processes, including software and data processing, from collection to validation. During the integration phase, incubator projects will facilitate a broader adoption by NFDI consortia while also supporting further development of the services. DMP4NFDI will increase its consultancy-style support to create templates and offer support for outreach measures. SMPs will complement the work done around DMPs, facilitating DMP/SMP interoperability. Furthermore, the integration phase will also look into alignment with EOSC.

Der Basisdienst DMP4NFDI unterstützt die NFDI Konsortien bei der Bereitstellung von Diensten für Datenmanagementpläne, Softwaremanagementpläne oder analoge Konzepte. DMP4NFDI hostet hierzu eine mandantenfähige RDMO Instanz mit Mandanten, die community-spezifisch angepasst werden können. Der Service umfasst das Hosting des Open-Source-Tools RDMO an zentraler

Stelle, die Koordination und Unterstützung bei der Erstellung von Templates und der inhaltlichen Standardisierung sowie Beratung und Schulungen für die DMP/SMP-Verantwortlichen der Konsortien. Diese Maßnahmen zielen darauf ab, disziplinspezifische DMP-Templates in standardisierten, maschinenlesbaren und interoperablen Formaten zu erstellen und die Kommunikation zwischen den verschiedenen am FDM-Prozess beteiligten Stakeholdern und Diensten, sowie Prozesse wie Datenerfassung und -validierung zu unterstützen und zu verbessern. In der Integrationsphase dienen regelmäßige Ausschreibungen für Inkubatoren dazu, weitere Konsortien aufzunehmen und bei der Weiterentwicklung der Services zu unterstützen. DMP4NFDI weitet hierzu den Support zur Erstellung von Templates aus und bietet nun auch Unterstützung bei Outreach-Maßnahmen. Als weitere Themen werden SMPs und die Interoperabilität von DMPs und SMPs verstärkt in den Fokus genommen sowie die Einbindung und Interoperabilität mit der EOSC weiterentwickelt.

2 Summary of Initialisation Phase Results

2.1 Change in Background and Motivation since the start of the Initialisation Phase

Working together with our use cases during initialisation provided us with several valuable insights and we will continue this exchange during the integration phase. In addition to the use cases we identified for the service initialisation, we added two consortia, MaRDI and FAIRagro, to the service, as both had an urgent need for RDMO hosting and support.

To ensure the relevance of our offerings, DMP4NFDI organised several workshops and meetings to collect requirements and feedback from the consortia. This approach not only improved the template framework's usability but also strengthened trust and engagement with our service. Based on the collected requirements, we adapted the service to include support for community outreach measures and to provide extensive support for the initial template development. Consortia preferred to focus on the basic handling and adaptation of templates to their community-specific needs, while DMP4NFDI takes responsibility for the general implementation of these templates as catalogs in RDMO (Windeck et al., 2025). Supporting outreach measures will support the consortia in better establishing DMPs in their communities. In addition, we will pursue to integrate our template framework as an official NFDI standard to achieve a greater degree of obligatoriness for researchers. We developed KPIs for the integration phase and identified measures and features needed to collect those and integrated them into our working plan.

In an infra-dmp meeting in May 2024, we realised that software management plans (SMPs) receive too little attention compared to the importance of research software for a FAIR research infrastructure expressed, e.g. by DFG signing the Amsterdam Declaration (DFG, 2024). We decided to add a focus on SMPs to the integration phase by including colleagues from NFDI4DataScience (from ZB MED) as partners who have year-long experience and are well connected internationally regarding SMPs.

Instead of creating a separate work package for SMPs, we integrated them into almost all work packages, as the tasks are closely interconnected.

A major milestone for long-term sustainability of the open source software RDMO was the founding of the RDMO Association on Nov 19th, 2024 (RDMO, 2025). With more than 20 founding institutions committing to the software's future, RDMO is reinforced by a strong and active community in which we are closely embedded. This validation strengthens our choice of RDMO as the technical backbone for DMP4NFDI and provides assurance of long-term maintenance and development.

2.2 Results of Initialisation Phase

2.2.1 Interim report on requirements for finalisation of the initialisation phase

For detailed information please refer to the OpenProject attachment in the appendix.

a) **Requirements analysis (D1.4.1)**

Due: 9 months after start date | **Percent finished:** 80% | **Status:** running

Overview of relevant outcomes: We have gathered valuable insights and adjusted the service accordingly. We collected all technical requirements to set up the RDMO service.

Outlook: A survey on training needs of the consortia is in preparation and will be carried out soon.

b) **Software evaluation (D1.4.2)**

Due: 6 months after start date | **Percent finished:** 100% | **Status:** finished

Overview of relevant outcomes: RDMO has been evaluated in preparation of the initialisation phase; see overview in the appendix.

c) **Service design (D1.4.3)**

Due: 6 months after start date | **Percent finished:** 85% | **Status:** running

Overview of relevant outcomes: RDMO is based on an established technology stack. We adapted our training goals and service support levels based on consortia feedback.

Outlook: First version of a Service Level Agreement (SLA) in preparation.

d) **Service prototype (D1.4.4)**

Due: 12 months after start date | **Percent finished:** 75% | **Status:** running

Overview of relevant outcomes: Training concepts and the template framework have been tested and further developed in two workshops. RDMO runs productively for three consortia.

Outlook: Some additional integrations and plugins for RDMO are planned and will be finished until the end of the initialisation phase.

e) **Service piloting and user testing (D1.4.5)**

Due: 12 months after start date | **Percent finished:** 70% **Status:** running

Overview of relevant outcomes: Seven consortia are part of the DMP4NFDI service, three productive clients, four in a test environment. The template framework and training elements have

been tested in two workshops.

Outlook: Training material is further developed during initialisation with a workshop planned at the end of the phase. The same applies to the development of the template framework. A how-to guide and FAQs are in development.

2.2.2 Other

The team actively participated in several events and produced publications to promote the DMP4NFDI service to diverse audiences. Highlights include presentations at the 12th RDMO Community Meeting (Windeck et al., 2024c) and at the FDM@Campus conference (Schönau, 2024), which disseminated insights into the NFDI DMP Template Framework and engaged the broader RDM community. We contributed to the Base4NFDI Roadshow (DMP4NFDI, 2024) and presented at the Base4NFDI User Conference to engage and exchange with consortia (Windeck et al., 2024b). We explored strategies for coordinating local RDMO instances with the central NFDI instance during a workshop together with NFDI4Earth (Anders et al., 2024). Finally, the DMP4NFDI service proposal of the initialisation phase was published, thereby rendering the scope and objectives of the service transparent to all relevant communities (Diederichs et al., 2024).

2.3 Update on Technical Readiness Level (TRL) of the proposed Basic Service

The software RDMO is running productively for NFDI4ING, NFDI4Chem, and NFDI4Culture, while test environments have been set up for NFDI4Memory, NFDI4Earth, MaRDI and FAIRagro. Several plugins created by our institutions and others demonstrate that RDMO can be integrated with existing RDM service portfolios (Windeck et al., 2024a), including compatibility with the international RDA DMP Common Standard for machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs) (Miksa et al., 2020). The multi-tenant RDMO instance has been smoothly running for several years at ULB Darmstadt. Taking also into account the recent founding of the RDMO association, we estimate a TRL of 9 by the end of the integration phase.

Support and training services have been set up, and are actively used by several NFDI consortia. Extensive resources, including a first version of FAQs and a how-to guide, will be available by the beginning of 2025. We integrated training sessions in our workshops, which have been well received, and a first release of training materials is planned for March 2025. The support structure is operational, and we will add a submission form to our website to automate the creation and assignment of support tickets to responsible team members, based on helpdesk best practices shared by NFDI4Culture. The training and support services are expected to reach a TRL of 7 by the end of the initialisation phase.

The NFDI DMP Template Framework progressed during the initialisation phase with a focus on modularity and adaptability to meet consortia needs. Built on the maDMP standard, it supports tailored template creation while ensuring interoperability. The workshops and use cases led to the

identification of areas requiring refinement. The framework is assessed at a TRL of 6. Overall, we expect a TRL of 8 for the whole service at the end of the integration phase.

3 Working Concept for the development of the Basic Service

3.1 Service Integration Concept

For the integration phase we establish incubator projects, collaborations with basic services, integrate SMPs and foster interoperability with EOSC. During initialisation the multi-tenant RDMO instance at ULB Darmstadt was utilised, providing each participating consortium with its own dedicated client. We will establish a regular call for incubator projects every six months to add further consortia, following the example of IAM4NFDI (2024). Several consortia have already committed to an incubator project, so the first round starts immediately at the beginning of the integration phase. Including the implementing consortia and use cases of the initialisation phase, 16 out of 26 consortia are involved (see chapter 4 for an overview). The incubators concern various activities, based on the current development stages of the respective consortia: RDMO hosting, template development, training and community outreach support, or integration with other consortia services.

We will continue to pursue the integration of Basic Services. We have implemented IAM4NFDI login services for all our clients and particular community AAls for NFDI4Chem and NFDI4Culture. PIDs concern several aspects in DMP templates, e.g. ORCIDs for involved staff, IDs for instruments or DMP IDs. Therefore, DMPs are one focus topic in the integration phase of PID4NFDI (Bingert et al., 2024). In collaboration with TS4NFDI, the integration of terminology services within RDMO is planned, as this has been a requirement in our workshops. For SMPs we have agreed a collaboration with nfdi.software, since information on research software addressed in such a plan can be used to improve documentation and findability. In terms of training, we will be working with RDMTraining4NFDI to harmonise training development efforts.

The integration phase will add a focus on SMPs. Another ZB MED department contributes experience from work on SMPs (Alves et al., 2021) gathered in the ELIXIR context since 2020 (ELIXIR, n.d.a) and in NFDI4DataScience (supporting a machine-actionable version together with ELIXIR since 2023 (Castro et al., 2024b; Castro et al., 2024c)). Through hackathons (Castro et al., 2023a), tutorials (Castro et al., 2024a), and conferences (Giraldo et al., 2023), NFDI4DataScience has led the development of a maSMP schema, which is analogous to the maDMP standard. The NFDI DMP Template Framework is based on the maDMP standard and we are actively involved in the further development of the standard planned for next year (RDA DMP Common Standards WG, 2024). Updates to the maSMP schema will be aligned to efforts such as nfdi.software (nfdi.software, n.d.), NFDI Research Software Metadata Working Group (Castro et al., 2023b), and EOSC Opportunity Area 7 Expert Group on Research Software (EOSC, n.d.).

Regarding the EOSC interoperability framework, RWTH Aachen University Library participates in the EU-funded OSTrails project as national pilot for Germany (OSTrails,n.d.a). One aim of OSTrails is to develop an interoperability framework based on the maDMP standard and thereby help to align various internationally used DMP tools, including RDMO, and other tools (e.g. repositories, electronic lab books). Funding for the pilot will commence in August 2025, with necessary adaptations to align with the interoperability framework being realised. These results will be incorporated into the DMP4NFDI service laying the foundation for the integration of DMP4NFDI with EOSC.

We will continue collecting requirements in exchange with the consortia to iteratively improve our service, e.g. with our initialisation use cases NFDI4Biodiversity and NFDI4Earth. Providing usable and community-specific DMP and SMP services for the consortia during the integration phase is our main goal. As KPIs we therefore identified: the number of RDMO clients, the number of community DMP templates available, the number of registered users and DMPs created in RDMO, the number of support requests, and the number of training and workshops conducted.

3.2 Future Development and Ramp-up Outlook

The ramp-up phase will focus on scaling and refining the DMP4NFDI service to support diverse research communities while ensuring long-term sustainability, interoperability, and operational readiness. Building on existing efforts, this phase will further integrate the maDMP standard into European and international frameworks, such as the EOSC, through active participation in projects like OSTrails. These initiatives will strengthen connections with related infrastructures, particularly in areas like FAIR metrics (Wilkinson et al., 2018) and research software (EOSC, n.d.). Collaboration with initiatives like FAIR-IMPACT and adherence to their Research Software MetaData guidelines (FAIR-IMPACT, n.d.) and leveraging frameworks such as the FAIR4RS principles (RDA, 2022) will ensure that DMP4NFDI aligns with international best practices on research software.

The NFDI DMP Template Framework will be refined to maintain flexibility and compliance with evolving international standards. Our goal is to integrate the framework as an official NFDI standard during this phase. Scalability testing will ensure that the infrastructure can handle increasing workloads and client numbers. Expanded outreach and training programs will facilitate onboarding, leveraging tailored workshops and Train-The-Trainer (TTT) formats.

To ensure service quality and sustainability, we will collect and monitor KPIs, while formalised support structures, including a Service Level Agreement, will secure long-term reliability. A business model for our services will be developed during the ramp-up phase, containing different possibilities for the different services, i.e. hosting (e.g. preferred via a financing arrangement with the NFDI e.V. or alternatively a fee-based offer by ULB Darmstadt for the consortia), training and template support (e.g., via a federated support and training scheme within Base4NFDI or NFDI overall), software development and tool integration (e.g., via individual contracts or using the RDMO association as a

hub for pooling demands). We see IAM4NFDI's service description and operating concept as a role model for this (Gietz et al., 2024).

3.3 Risks and Challenges

Risk / Potential Impact	Affected WP	Mitigation Strategies
Increased complexity of requirements, e.g. growing expectations for interoperability, API integration, and heterogeneous discipline-specific needs (high probability)	WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4, WP6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Manage consortia needs via incubator projects with clear set goals and timelines to prevent scope expansion - Standardise solutions and identify synergies across consortia - Ensure framework adaptability for varying requirements as consortia join sequentially for collaboration - Develop a core framework with common ground and discipline-specific extensions
Difficulties integrating the service into EOSC leading to missed synergies with other European initiatives (medium probability)	WP7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Early alignment with, identification and use of existing EOSC services/requirements/standards, based on participation in OSTRails project - Active participation in EOSC events (e.g. connectivity workshop twice a year)
High demand for training and workshops (medium probability)	WP5, WP6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop re-usable TTT concepts and material published as Open Educational Resources (OER)
Researcher's reluctance incorporating DMP practices (high probability)	WP2, WP3, WP4, WP6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop discipline-specific DMP/SMP templates in incubator projects - Increase added value by integrating the DMP4NFDI services with other consortia services - Support consortia in outreach and awareness activities - Establish official DMP standard in the NFDI
Limited personnel resources in the consortia for DMP services (medium probability)	WP3, WP4, WP6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide resources and trainings for easy uptake - Engage consortia early in development - Offer flexible consortium-specific adjustments - Promote collaboration between consortia

4 Support Actions from Base4NFDI / NFDI Sections, and Integrating NFDI Consortia / Efforts

Support from	Work package / Description of contribution	Contact person Basic Service
Base4NFDI	Support in organising training and outreach, reporting, and EOSC interoperability.	
Basic Service TS4NFDI	Integrating TS4NFDI and DMP4NFDI	
Basic Service PID4NFDI	PIDs in NFDI DMP Template Framework	
Basic Service nfdi.software	Integrating nfdi.software and DMP4NFDI based on SMPs	
Basic Service RDMTraining4NFDI	Integrating RDMTraining4NFDI and DMP4NFDI training	

Table 2: Support needed from Base4NFDI / Service Stewards / Section

Support from	Involved effort	Consortium (contact)
NFDI4Microbiota, NFDI4Health, NFDI4Energy, NFDI4BIOIMAGE, NFDI-MatWerk	Participation in incubator project for hosting RDMO client	
MaRDI	Participation in incubator project for RDMO service integration	
FAIRagro, NFDI4Culture, NFDI4Memory, Text+	Participation in incubator project for template development	
DataPLANT	Participation in incubator project for software management plans	
NFDI4Chem	Participation in incubator project for community outreach	

Table 3: Contributions required from the integrating consortia

5 Work Programme

DMP/SMP Tool Hosting, Template Standardisation, Support and Training for NFDI Consortia

Figure 1: Overview of work packages interaction with community and NFDI

5.1 Overview of Work Packages

Work package	Deliverables (D) and milestones (M)	Responsible partner
WP1 Project Management & Incubator Projects Organisation	M1.1: First call for incubator projects D1.1: Report on service usage statistics and incubator projects	Lead: TUDa ZB MED, RWTH Aachen UL
WP 2 Community Engagement & Communication	M2.1: Service Roadshow developed D2.1: Concept for outreach support D2.2: Knowledge Base on service website	Lead: ZB MED RWTH Aachen UL, TUDa
WP3 Train-The-Trainer & Capacity Building	M3.1: Successful TTT session with revised material D3.1: Publication of revised version of TTT concept including SMPs D3.2: Publication of revised training materials as OERs	Lead: ZB MED
WP4 RDMO Plugin Management & Service Integration	D4.1: Plugin management feature D4.2: Integration of Terminology Services with RDMO D4.3: Plugin to exchange metadata with nfdi.software basic service	Lead: TUDa
WP5 RDMO Hosting & Feature Development	D5.1: Hosting RDMO for first round of incubator projects D5.2: Feature to collect and visualise user statistics D5.3: Features to improve catalog development for clients	Lead: TUDa

WP6 Consortia Template Support	M6.1: Integration of SMP in the Template Framework D6.1: RDMO ontology supporting machine-actionability D6.2: Checklist for standardised extensions of templates	Lead: RWTH Aachen UL ZB MED
WP7 Internationalisation	D7.1: Integrate OSTrails pilots into DMP4NFDI D7.2: Report on reuse of integrations via OSTrails	Lead: RWTH Aachen UL ZB MED

Table 4: Overall work programme with work packages, deliverables, milestones, and responsible partner.

5.2 Detailed Work Programme

5.2.1 WP1 Project Management & Incubator Projects Organisation

During initialisation, the project partners established project management via OpenProject, regular meetings, and a monthly Jour Fixe for consortia as users of the service. We will refine our operating model and develop and report KPIs. WP1 includes reporting to and exchange with Base4NFDI, the section Common Infrastructures and its working groups, especially infra-dmp. For the integration of new consortia, we will organise a regular call for incubator projects with consortia twice a year. Incubator projects aim at bringing the community closer to RDMO but also improving interoperability between RDMO and other consortia-specific tools for management plans. Incubator projects are assigned to working packages depending on their focus topic: RDMO hosting, template development, training and community outreach support, or integration with other consortia services.

- WP1 Milestone 1: First call for incubator projects
- WP1 Deliverable 1: Report on service usage statistics and incubator projects

5.2.2 WP2 Community Engagement & Communication

This work package focuses on outreach activities to raise awareness and promote adoption among NFDI consortia and Basic Services, as well as other stakeholders, showcasing the capabilities of DMP4NFDI. It accompanies incubator projects related to outreach. Key activities comprise low-barrier introductory events to demonstrate DMP and SMP value supported by RDMO, including targeted presentations, live demos, and quick-start guides. This outreach support for consortia will occur at consortium meetings, conferences, and other events, including a DMP4NFDI Roadshow with low barrier entry level and general introductions, demonstrations, and onboarding information. Outreach and awareness activities will be first summarised in a concept and implemented together with WP3 and WP6, in close coordination with the Base4NFDI team. For communication, regular updates via newsletters and the DMP4NFDI website will keep users informed of developments and success stories. Rocket.Chat will support asynchronous exchanges, and our website will feature a knowledge base (e.g., How-Tos, FAQs, best practices and low-threshold introductions of the service) and an inquiry input-form integrated with our technical support system.

- WP2 Milestone 1: Service Roadshow developed

- WP2 Deliverable 1: Concept for outreach support
- WP2 Deliverable 2: Knowledge Base on service website

5.2.3 WP3 Train-The-Trainer & Capacity Building

Based on general feedback, challenges, and requirements collected from the consortia during the initialisation phase and in alignment with RDMTraining4NFDI, we are developing a TTT concept alongside training materials as OERs. The concept includes topics such as introduction to DMPs, the RDMO architecture with its underlying data model, its hierarchies, relationships and their dependencies, and the RDMO interface for template creation and usage. In WP3, we will further develop, implement, and adapt the concept by including new units (e.g. training on SMPs) for consortia staff responsible for conveying DMPs/SMPs. Further training approaches such as training hackathons, comprehensive in-depth sessions on consortia-specific DMP/SMP topics, and short micro-training sessions (5-15 minutes) on RDMO topics will be developed to meet different needs. The TTT concept will also provide an introduction and training on the usage of the NFDI DMP Template Framework in RDMO. Close collaboration with WP2 will ensure that outreach and awareness activities effectively promote the main objective of the TTT concept and attract new potential consortia collaborations. Jointly organised training sessions together with WP6 will be offered, as part of incubator projects and targeted events. All training materials will be made available as OER to encourage consortia staff to reuse it as trainers and disseminate the knowledge independently in their community.

- WP3 Milestone 1: Successful TTT session with revised material
- WP3 Deliverable 1: Publication of revised version of TTT concept including SMPs
- WP3 Deliverable 2: Publication of revised training materials as OERs

5.2.4 WP4 RDMO Plugin Management & Service Integration

During initialisation, we integrated existing plugins and developed prototypes for service integration and collected requirements from our use cases and other consortia in workshops and meetings. Connecting RDMO to the IAM4NFDI service was achieved for different community AAls. One requirement is to add terminology support to RDMO, which we will implement as part of an incubator project with the basic service TS4NFDI. Together with the basic service nfdi.software we will explore how SMPs in RDMO can improve software documentation and findability, and how both services can support each other by exchanging metadata. Furthermore, we identified a need to establish a plugin management that gives the consortia more control over plugins and settings. In addition, we will continue supporting consortia to integrate our service with the service portfolios of the consortia in incubator projects. MaRDI, for example, wants to add resources for instruments to their template and plugin, NFDIxCs to establish a connection to the RDM Container (Al Laban et al., 2023), and NFDI4Microbiota and NFDI4Health are planning to connect services like repositories with RDMO. In the context of the OStrails project, the UL Aachen will work on integrations with electronic lab

notebooks such as Chemotion.net and eLabFTW. These developments are also interesting for NFDI consortia and will be added to the service as needed by the clients. All plugins and features will be made available under open license.

- WP4 Deliverable 1: Plugin management feature
- WP4 Deliverable 2: Integration of Terminology Services with RDMO
- WP4 Deliverable 3: Plugin to exchange metadata with nfdi.software basic service

5.2.5 WP5 RDMO Hosting & Feature Development

At present, seven consortia are part of the DMP4NFDI RDMO service, three productive clients (NFDI4Ing, NFDI4Chem, NFDI4Culture) and four test clients (FAIRagro, MaRDI, NFDI4Earth, NFDI4Memory). Test clients are used for template preparation and will remain available to the consortia to prepare template updates or testing plugins in the future. We established a checklist and workflow to add new RDMO clients. Additional consortia have already expressed their interest in RDMO hosting in incubator projects (NFDI4Microbiota, NFDI4Health, NFDI4BIOIMAGE, NFDI4Energy, NFDI-MatWerk), and we will continue to add consortia during the integration phase based on the regular incubator calls. In addition, we will also add features to the service as requested by the consortia during our workshops and exchange meetings (Windeck et al., 2025), e.g. more control over user roles & rights and improving the management interface to simplify catalog updates and development to complement the use of the DMP template framework further developed in WP6. Another feature concerns the collection and visualising of user statistics which will also be utilised for the KPI reporting.

- WP5 Deliverable 1: Hosting RDMO for first round of incubator projects
- WP5 Deliverable 2: Feature to collect and visualise user statistics
- WP5 Deliverable 3: Features to improve catalog development for clients

5.2.6 WP6 Consortia Template Support

Although DMPs and SMPs share some core elements across consortia, domain-specific versions are closer to the community and better serve their needs. DMP4NFDI provides the NFDI DMP Template Framework which comprises a set of all-purpose questions and a common vocabulary to ensure interoperability between different templates. Consortia will be supported in using the framework to create their own domain-specific templates by selecting, adjusting, grouping, and organising the questions relevant to them.

We will integrate the work done around maSMPs (maSMP, n.d.), which provides an extension to schema.org covering the case of SMPs. This will result in new questions and attributes in the framework. To facilitate the inclusion of domain-specific information, we will create a controlled vocabulary in the form of an ontology, making it easier to maintain the framework, which will be aligned to the proposed ontology. We will pursue our goal of integrating the framework as an official NFDI standard, as discussed in an infra-dmp meeting on Nov 24, 2023. In collaboration with WP3

we develop a checklist for creating discipline-specific extensions, documentation and training materials, and derive feature requests improving the RDMO interface in order to simplify the use of the framework to be developed by WP5. Incubator projects for DMPs are planned with NFDI4Culture and NFDI4Objects, both currently developing a common template, with NFDI4Memory, FAIRagro, and Text+. For SMPs, incubators with DataPLANT and NFDIxCS are planned. We will monitor and document the development process in order to derive general findings and pitfalls. Best practices will serve as examples for other consortia.

- WP6 Milestone 1: Integration of SMP in the Template Framework
- WP6 Deliverable 1: RDMO ontology supporting machine-actionability
- WP6 Deliverable 2: Checklist for standardised extensions of templates

5.2.7 WP7 Internationalisation

DMP4NFDI aligns to international efforts such as EOSC OSTrails (OSTrails, n.d.a), the work done by the RDA DMP Common Standards WG (2024), and ELIXIR Software Best Practices (ELIXIR (n.d.b)). DMP4NFDI work around machine-actionability supported by the RDMO ontology will facilitate DMP/SMP information exchange with efforts such as the ELIXIR Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW, n.d.) and the corresponding version for SMPs, and DMP tools adopting the RDA DMP Common Standards initiative. We will get involved in the update of the maDMP standard and participate in the RDA DMP common standards working group.

A first compliance analysis has revealed that RDMO is well positioned to accommodate the OSTrails Interoperability Framework (Suchanek, 2024). Once this framework is established, the alignment will be carried out within the OSTrails project, planned to be completed by Q1/2026 (Spichtinger et al., 2024, p. 57-60). DMP4NFDI takes advantage of this work at OSTrails by adopting the Horizon Europe pilot as well as selected thematic pilots (physics, marine/coastal, social sciences and humanities, biodiversity, language resources, and astronomy and partially physics) depending on the feedback by corresponding NFDI consortia (OSTrails, n.d.b). This also paves the way to a potential service at the future NFDI EOSC node. The new extension towards SMPs can also be transferred to the OSTrails community, thus facilitating international adoption of this important topic. The RDMO Ontology and template framework also adopt and align to EOSC initiatives such as FAIR metrics (as some of the questions would support some FAIR aspects related to PIDs and metadata), and, in particular for SMPs, developments on the recently created Opportunity Area 7 on Research Software (EOSC, n.d.).

- WP7 Deliverable 1: Integrate OSTrails pilots into DMP4NFDI
- WP7 Deliverable 2: Report on reuse of integrations via OSTrails

5.2.8 Gantt chart

Figure 2: Gantt chart for work programme

Appendix

a) Bibliography and list of references

Al Laban, F., Bernoth, J., Goedicke, M., Lucke, U., Striewe, M., Wieder, P., & Yahyapour, R. (2023). Establishing the Research Data Management Container in NFDI4CS. *Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure*, <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.395>

Alves, R., Bampalikis, D., Castro, L., Fernández, J. M., Harrow, J., Kuzak, M., ... Via, A. (2021). ELIXIR Software Management Plan for Life Sciences.

<https://doi.org/10.37044/osf.io/k8znb>

Anders, I., Diederichs, K., Fuchs, H., Getzlaff, K., Gonzalez-Ocanto, M., Henzen, C., Schmidt, C., Schönau, S., Thiemann, S., Wallace, D., & Windeck, J. (2024a). NFDI4Earth x DMP4NFDI Basic Service Online Workshop 2024 Report. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14534702>

Bingert, S., Böhm, J., Buys, M., El-Gebali, S., Genderjahn, S., Hagemann-Wilholt, S., Kahlert, T., Lange, M., Meistring, M., Sens, I., & Stocker, M. (2024). Persistent Identifier Services for the German National Research Data Infrastructure: Proposal for the Integration Phase of Base4NFDI. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14281255>

Castro, L. J., Geist, L., Gonzalez, E., Gonzalez-Ocanto, M., Grossmann, Y. V., Pronk, T., Solanki, D., Utrilla Guerrero, C., Wallace, D., & Windeck, J. (2023a). Five Minutes to Write a Software Management Plan – A Machine-actionable Approach to Simplify the Creation of SMPs. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10374839>

Castro, L. J., Ferez, S., Fuhrmans, M., Göpfert, J., Iglezakis, D., Karras, O., & Struck, A. (2023b). "Research Software Metadata" - Working Group Charter (NFDI section-metadata). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10246218>

Castro, L. J. (2024a). Introduction and tutorial on Metadata and SMPs for FAIR research software. 47th German Conference on Artificial Intelligence (KI 2024), Würzburg, Germany. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13799879>

Castro L. J., Giraldo O., Geist L., Quiñones N., Solanki D., & Rebholz-Schuhmann D. (2024b). machine-actionable Software Management Plan Ontology (maSMP Ontology) (2.1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10582073>

Castro, L. J., Giraldo, O., Geist, L., Quiñones, N., Solanki, D., & Rebholz-Schuhmann, D. (2024c). Usage guidance (aka profiles) for the machine-actionable Software Management Plan Ontology (2.1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10582121>

DFG (2024). Signing of the “Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software

Sustainability". <https://www.dfg.de/en/news/news-topics/announcements-proposals/2024/ifr-24-114>

Diederichs, K., Förstner, K., Hausen, D., Jagusch, G., Johannsen, J., Lindstädt, B., Schmitz, D., Schönau, S., Stäcker, T., & Windeck, J. (2024). DMP4NFDI - NFDI Basic Service for Data Management Plans (1.0.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13445355>

DMP4NFDI (2024). Services Roadshow by Base4NFDI - DMP4NFDI.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Gw5qoD-sCxc>

DSW (n.d.). Data Stewardship Wizard. <https://ds-wizard.org/>

ELIXIR (n.d.a). <https://www.elixir-europe.org/>

ELIXIR (n.d.b). Software development best practices for Life Sciences. <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/tools/software-best-practices>

EOSC (n.d.). OA7: Research Software. <https://eosc.eu/opportunity-area-exp/oa7-research-software/>

FAIR-IMPACT (n.d.). The Research Software MetaData Guidelines for End-Users. <https://fair-impact.github.io/RSMD-guidelines/>

Gietz, P., Hardt, M., Hübner, D., Pempe, W., Pohl, C., Bonn, M., & Apweiler, S. (2024). IAM4NFDI Service description, operating concept and TOMs (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13149756>

Giraldo, O., Dessi, D., Dietze, S., Rebholz-Schuhmann, D., & Castro, L. J. (2023). Machine-Actionable Metadata for Software and Software Management Plans for NFDI. *Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.279>

IAM4NFDI (2024). NFDI AAI Documentation. <https://nfdi-aa1.de/incubators/>

maSMP (n.d.). maSMP Project. <https://zbmed-semtec.github.io/maSMPs/>

Miksa, T., Walk, P., & Neish, P. (2020). RDA DMP Common Standard for Machine-actionable Data Management Plans. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00039>

nfdi.software (n.d.). <https://base4nfdi.de/projects/nfdi-software>

OSTrails (n.d.a). <https://ostrails.eu/dmps>, <https://ostrails.eu/>

OSTrails (n.d.b). <https://ostrails.eu/case-studies>

RDA DMP Common Standards WG (2024). DMP Common Standard for maDMPs Maintenance. <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/dmp-common-standards-wg/posts/?post=171294>

RDA (2022). FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS Principles). <https://www.rd-alliance.org/sites/default/files/FAIR%20Principles%20for%20Research%20Software%20%28FAIR4RS%20Principles%29.pdf>

RDMO (2025): Gründungsversammlung des RDMO-Vereins.

https://www.forschungsdaten.org/index.php/Gr%C3%BCndungsversammlung_des_RDMO-Vereins

Schönau, S. (2024). DMP4NFDI - ein NFDI Basisdienst im Bereich Datenmanagementpläne.

Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/records/14007397>

Spichtinger, D., López Lériida, J. und Papadopoulou, E. (2024) D4.1: Pilots Methodology and Operational Processes. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13880731>

Suchánek, M. (2024) D2.1: Analysis of the OSTrails Interoperability Framework Tools Compliance. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13880235>

Wilkinson, M., Sansone, SA., Schultes, E. (2018). A design framework and exemplar metrics for FAIRness. Sci Data 5, 180118. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2018.118>

Windeck, J., Schröder, M., Frenzel, J., Kusmierz, S., Fuchs, H., & Klar, J. (2024a).

Connecting RDM Services: Interoperability and Interfaces for RDMO. Bausteine

Forschungsdatenmanagement, (2), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.17192/bfdm.2024.2.8629>

Windeck, J., Diederichs, K., Schönau, S., Wallace, D. (2024b). DMP4NFDI - a Basic Service for Data Management Planning.

https://events.gwdg.de/event/658/contributions/2354/attachments/757/1617/10_DMP4NFDI_-_a_Basic_Service_for_Data_Management_Planing.pdf

Windeck, J., Diederichs, K., Schönau, S. (2024c). Infra-dmp & DMP4NFDI.

<https://www.forschungsdaten.org/images/1/14/2024-10-08-infra-dmp-DMP4NFDI.pdf>

Windeck, J., Gonzalez Ocanto, M., Diederichs, K., Schönau, S., & Wallace, D. (2025).

Collecting DMP Requirements for NFDI - Report on DMP4NFDI activities (1.0.0). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14643349>